

Review Article

Instructional Materials and English Language Teaching in the Classrooms: Criteria for Consideration

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Abstract

Recent years have seen a dramatic increase in the use of commercially produced foreign language course books as core teaching materials in young learner classrooms. In many cases, the approaches taken and the methods advocated in these materials are accepted uncritically by the teachers using them regardless of their teaching context. Teachers in some contexts also do not have a choice and are forced to 'teach the book' and implement methodologies that they may not agree with. However, in both cases there is a huge risk of not doing what is best to promote learning. To avoid this possibility a more critical stance towards language learning materials is needed. This paper presents the concept of instructional materials, then presents a classification of teaching materials, importance of instructional materials, some criteria for selection of instructional materials and lastly discusses the general criteria for the evaluation of English Language learning resources.

Keywords: Instructional Materials, English Language, Teaching in the Classrooms, and Criteria for consideration

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Introduction

Instructional or teaching material is as important as teaching and learning, hence its relevance in the field of education cannot be overemphasized. It stimulates learners' interest, make teaching and learning more productive, provide meaningful sources of information, extend human experience, makes learning more concrete, real and immediate; to mention but a few. The quality of teaching material goes a long way in enhancing or inhibiting teaching and learning and it is therefore necessary to evaluate a material to ascertain its suitability and relevance to achieving the objectives of the lesson for which it is designed. In the case of human resource, evaluation is also conducted to ascertain how well the person knows the content of the lesson to be taught before he or she goes to teach the learners.

Concept of Instructional Materials

Teaching materials are both human and non-human instructional resources which teachers use in the course of teaching. Some are factory-made and some are improvised by the teacher but they all serve the same purpose (Iorliam, 2013, p.57). Also, Udom (2013) sees instructional material as "a list of all equipment and materials needed for that particular lesson which the teacher will provide." As educators guide students' learning, they must consider the goals and outcomes of the curricula; the backgrounds, abilities, interests, and learning styles of individual students; and, the learning resources available. Instructional resources and materials cover what a teacher uses to teach so as to involve the five senses of sight, hearing, touch, smell and taste while presenting his lessons. Resources could be human or non-human. Instructional materials are very important in language teaching, especially foreign language. Hence, they facilitate the direct relationship between the sounds and their symbols and also words and the objects they represent. The use of instructional material reduces the problem associated with learning by making teaching and learning concrete rather than abstract. Instructional materials help to clearly illustrate abstract concepts in a language class. The teacher of language is responsible for the selection of adequate teaching materials. Although the school authority is responsible for the purchase and installation of instructional materials, it is the responsibility of the teacher who knows the content of his lessons to select adequate and relevant instructional materials. The teacher henceforth improvises any teaching material that is not available.

The provision and effective use of high-quality learning resources facilitate students' construction of understanding through inquiry so they are better able to explore, question, identify, organise, analyse, synthesize, and evaluate information. Azikiwe

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(2007) sees instructional or teaching materials, as the objects and substances that are used by teachers to enable them to teach efficiently and concretely. In other words, instructional materials or resources are the teaching aids which teachers employ to enhance the quality and efficiency of teaching for easy and effective understanding of the learning. While materials are strictly non-human aids, teaching resources may even refer to human beings that may be used for the purpose of teaching. The selection of instructional material is solely the responsibility of the teacher.

Learning resources are generally understood to be texts, videos, software, and other materials that assist students to meet the expectations for learning, as defined by provincial or local curricula. Before a learning resource is used in a classroom, it must be evaluated to ensure that criteria such as those for curriculum match, social considerations and age or developmental appropriateness are met. Learning resources such as newspapers or periodicals that support current events or “the teachable moment” also need to be evaluated for suitability before use in a classroom. Usually, the evaluation of this type of resource relies on the professional expertise and judgement of the classroom teacher.

Classification of Teaching Materials

According to Azikwe (2007), there are three broad types of grouping of instructional materials

1. Visual
2. Audio
3. Audio -visual

Visuals

These are resource materials that appeal to the sense of sight and touch as well as the sense of smell. They consist of:

1. Non - projected materials: chalk board, adhesives
2. Pictorial materials : charts, pictures
3. Mobile materials
4. Three - dimensional aids and materials
5. Projected materials
6. Film - striped and slide projector
7. Laboratory equipment, chemicals and apparatus
8. Books.

Audio

The aural materials are instructional materials that appeal to the senses of hearing and touch. They are:

1. Records and record players
2. Tapes and tape recorders
3. Language laboratories
4. Radio

Audio-Visuals

Learning materials that fall under audio-visuals appeal to the senses of sight, hearing and touch. They are:

1. Sound-stripe projector
2. Television
3. Video-tape recorder

Importance of Instructional Materials

Instructional materials cover whatever the teacher uses to involve all the senses of sight, hearing, touch, smell and taste while presenting his lessons (Oyinloye, 2007). They are very important in language teaching, especially the foreign languages, because they facilitate the direct association between sounds and their symbols and also words and the objects they represent. The use of aids reduces to the minimum, the problems of interference and translation. They also help to vividly illustrate meanings of entities because they are associated with materials used by the teacher to improve the quality of his teaching.

Instructional Materials' Relevance

Tomlinson (1998) says that the teaching materials have a crucial role in developing quality of education. (Ijert 2015). It is important to remember, however that there has been a moment to make learners the centre of language instruction since 1960's, it's probably best to view teaching materials as resources in achieving aims and objectives that have already been set in terms of learner needs because teaching materials should always be at the service of the teachers and learners (Brown, 1994). Consequently , teachers need to make every necessary effort to establish and apply a wide variety of relevant and contextually appropriate criteria for the evaluation of the materials that they use in their language class rooms in order to accommodate the needs of learners and `` the aims , methods and values of the teaching program''

Criteria for the selection of Instructional materials

Instructional material to be used by any language teacher must meet the following criteria as suggested by Azikiwe (2007):

1. **Relevance:** It must be relevant to the topic or the content to be taught. An instructional material or resource is usually evaluated before selection in order to ascertain its relevance in the topic to be taught. It is worthy of note that any material that must be used to teach a particular topic must be related to the topic in order to give an expected result or lead to the achievement of the learning objectives. The instructional or resource materials to be selected must be relevant to the objectives as well as to the target population (i.e. the learners) for whom the materials are to be used. This is important because the objectives that the materials are designed to achieve should be similar to those that the teacher and the learners are trying to achieve. Being relevant to the learner means that the characteristics of the learner such as age, level of attainment or maturation, ability, aptitude and capability, should all be borne in mind to enable the teacher select relevant materials to their need, interests and aspirations.
2. **Usability:** It must be previewed and gotten used to by the teacher that would make use of it. A teacher should be able to use any instructional material he or she is taking to the classroom. On the other hand, any material that is designed for the learners must be what they can use. Evaluation therefore, helps to ascertain the usability of the material.
3. **Acceptability:** According to Azikiwe (2007), it must be acceptable in other places for the same lesson or topic. A teaching material to be used by a teacher to teach is what other teachers in another place can also use to teach the same or similar topic. However, a teaching material to be selected should also be what is acceptable in the learning environment.
4. **Suitability:** teaching resources or materials must be suitable for the age and intellectual level of the learners. Based on this, the learner's age is one of the most important factors to consider while selecting or evaluating teaching materials. This is very important because any material beyond the scope and intellectual level of the learners will yield little or no result when used to teach them. For examples, a teacher of primary six cannot use teaching material designed for secondary or university students to teach primary six. The material may be complex for the young learners.

5. **Availability:** An important criterion for selection and use of resource materials availability of the needed materials .In other words, before the teacher decides on materials to use, he must be certain that they are available as well as accessible to him and the learners. More often than not, the best materials to be used are not available due to lack of fund. Herein, lays the need for every teacher to avail himself of the skills for improvisation of “Instructional materials. If the need arises the materials could be improvised. The teacher does not decide to use any materials just because it has been theoretically stated that the materials are effective for teaching a particular topic whereas they are not physically available. Rather, the availability of the materials should be ascertained before the decision to use them. Availability implies, therefore, that the resources to be used must be physically provided and made accessible both to teachers and learners as when needed. Secondly, consideration should be given to the possibility of having enough for members of the class to be equitably involved in the class activities. Furthermore, materials might require other special facilities such as recorder, socket, adaptors, electricity, etc. before they could be used. The teacher should therefore ascertain that everything needed for the use of a material is available and within easy reach to him and to the learners before it is selected. The question form for this criterion is: are the needed instructional materials available and accessible to teachers and learners?

6. **Practicability:** a teaching material must be easily understood and practicable for the learners. In the case of selection of reading texts, the texts should be what the learners can use even without the supervision of the teacher. Learning resources play a significant role in shaping students’ views about themselves and the world. Therefore, it is important that these resources portray respect and dignity for both genders, for those in specific cultural groups, for people with varying physical and intellectual abilities, for people of various ages, and for people of differing sexual orientation.

The Following General Principles serve as guidelines throughout the Learning Resources Evaluation Process as outlines by Adeosun (2007):

1. Learning resources that address current curriculum priorities and educational policies are to be included, where appropriate and available, on all lists of learning resources.
2. Where numerous resources are available on a particular topic, only resources of the highest quality are recommended.

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3. Resources on controversial issues are necessary to support student achievement of particular curriculum outcomes.
4. Learning resources are evaluated on their overall merit.
5. Resource-based learning is advisable therefore it is necessary that several media formats including fiction and non-fiction print, audio-visual resources, electronic resources both online and those in physical formats, multi-resource packages, manipulative, and games.

Material Evaluation

Material evaluation tries to ascertain the appropriateness of a teaching material to teach a specific course. Material evaluation is very crucial. Wrongly designed teaching materials can cripple the academic and career competence of students unless they are developed carefully and evaluated periodically. It is pertinent to up-date the content of teaching materials. Clarity of instruction is a useful starting point in material evaluation; often teachers' book gives supporting grammar advice, but the real working of materials lies in students' instruction. Firstly, activities and tasks need to be understandable, something that will be clear to learners. This moves onto the next most important and intertwine factor which is task-achievability, if tasks materials provided cannot be realised, they need to be decisively removed. Tasks need to be evaluated for content. The following questions may be asked in doing that:

- i. Is it culturally acceptable?
- ii. Are the materials practical?
- iii. Are the materials teachable?
- iv. Are the materials flexible?
- v. Do the materials build confidence to achieve students' independence?

Materials can be systematically evaluated to make daily teaching organised and rewarding. For example: when choosing a course book, it can be evaluated by looking at all the task within a unit and check if they are offering students a variety of task types, genres, inputs, outputs, skills and a variety of factors that add to the effectiveness of the unit's content. Course books can be evaluated as a whole, considering other factors such as: cohesion of units and recycling of language to ascertain if a book would be a helpful addition to a school's syllabus. A useful question to evaluation to consider necessary and desirable features of proposed materials, desirable features should be classified as extremely desirable, very desirable and quite desirable. More general questions can be asked about teaching contexts in which material will be used. Other important factors in the evaluation process are the time available to students, age, students' interests, students' background, class size and students' level. Course books

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offer “a coherent syllabus, satisfactory language control, motivating text, audio, CDs and other accessories such as video, DVD material, CD ROMs and extra resource material.” According to Ur (2012) course books may be the most “powerful device” in relation to methodological innovations and revolutions in syllabus design. Choosing the right the right course book can therefore have countless rewarding effects in the classroom.

The revision will open the door to incorporate newly emerged thoughts to the contents, methodology and social issues included in the teaching materials. In addition, a teaching material needs to be evaluated or revised from time to time in order to ascertain its suitability and relevance to teaching in the growing trends in education. In doing this, recent thoughts and findings in the area of language can be incorporated.

General Criteria for the Evaluation of Language Learning Resources

Evaluation criteria focus on curriculum fit, content, instructional design, technical considerations, and social considerations. (Please note the evaluation forms that follow within this section.)

1. Physical quality

Learning resources offer durability and high quality physical and technical quality. They are appealing to the intended audience.

2. Content:

Learning resources are well organized and of high quality. They offer content that is current, accurate, and authentic.

3. Social consideration:

Learning resources are fair and equitable concerning age, ability, culture, gender, socio- economic status, religion, occupation, and sexual orientation. They are free from bias as reasonably possible, and they are appropriate for the general age and maturity level of the audience. Also, learning resources are free of intrusive advertising.

4. Instructional design:

Learning resources are user-friendly. Learning resources foster deeper understanding of the subject being addressed. They relate to the curriculum and are consistent with its philosophy. They are reasonable regarding expected classroom time commitments. For example, lengthy sequential programmes that

must be taught from beginning to end to be effective tend to tack time away from teaching the curriculum and are not recommended.

5. Qualification of developer:

Learning resources should be developed and validated by qualified and reputable people.

Conclusion

The role of instructional materials in classroom teaching and learning activities cannot be overemphasized. Instructional material evaluation is formative. It is a systematic process that needs to be carefully done; as this will to a large extent foster or hinder effective teaching and learning. Evaluation as a process will help a teacher to know the most suitable and relevant instructional material to select. It will also make the teacher know how well the students learnt with a material previously used. It is neither likely nor expected that one evaluation system can be used successfully to evaluate all English Language instructional materials. There will be differences in systems designed for materials intended for different grade bands and/or for different English Language disciplines. The guidelines described above provide guidance for developing rigorous and consistent evaluation systems. These guidelines show that the tools and processes must work together to gather evidence for the quality of the materials, provide opportunities for evaluators to discuss and build consensus, and provide a neutral, equal platform to compare the strengths and limitations of the various instructional materials used in English Language education.

Suggestions

To make teaching and learning worthwhile, it is suggested that the government should employ the use of appropriate instructional materials and appropriate teachers because adequate instructional materials demand appropriate management. And where the available materials are to be evaluated and developed before usage or after, experts should be engaged to carry out the job in order to achieve the needed competency in the teaching and learning of the English language in Nigeria. For us to achieve enhancement and innovations in higher education in Nigeria, the English language should be properly taught. The instructional materials that facilitate teaching and learning of the English language should be adequately evaluated and developed hence competency in the English language helps in the understanding of other courses. And above all, the English language is so vital in Nigeria being the language of

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instruction in our institutions of higher learning, language of publication, governance and international relations.

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